

ACTIVITY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN THE SECURITIES MARKET

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Annotation: This article provides an opinion on the activities of commercial banks in the securities market, where the understanding of such processes as the sale or purchase of securities by commercial banks is presented.

Keywords: Commercial banks, securities, treasury obligations, certificates of deposit, shares, bonds.

The activity of commercial banks in the stock market is taken as a whole **banking license** is carried out in There is only one restriction regarding the specialists of commercial banks who carry out operations related to securities. They must attend the course "operations on precious securities" organized by the Ministry of Finance and receive qualification diplomas with the names of stock market specialists.

Table 1

The functions of the bank securities portfolio can be classified as follows:

No	Functions and their definition
1	<i>Ensuring the profitability of the bank regardless of changes in the operational phase:</i> the decrease in income from loans can be offset by income from securities.
2	<i>Compensation of credit risks in the portfolio of bank loans.</i> High-quality securities can be purchased and held to offset the risk of bank loans.
3	<i>Ensuring geographic diversification.</i> The fact that securities are generally more regionally related (or nationwide) than bank loan objects creates an opportunity for effective diversification of bank income.
4	<i>Ensuring liquidity.</i> Stocks can be sold to obtain the necessary cash or used by the bank in the form of collateral (for example, pawn loans) to attract additional funds.
5	<i>Use as collateral.</i> Securities can be used in the form of security of deposits of the government, local government bodies in the bank.
6	<i>Protecting the bank from losses.</i> It is used to protect against losses that may occur due to changes in market interest rates.
7	<i>Ensuring "resilience" of the bank's asset portfolio.</i> Investment securities (relative to bank loans) can be quickly bought or sold to restructure bank assets in accordance with current market conditions.

8	<i>Bringing the indicators of the bank balance to the required level. The high quality inherent in most securities ensures that the bank's balance sheet complies with established regulations.</i>
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In order to increase their financial stability, commercial banks operate as the largest brokers and dealers in the stock market of Uzbekistan. Many commercial banks in Uzbekistan form a portfolio of securities by investing their funds in various financial instruments. In this case, the bank forms a portfolio of highly liquid and high-yield funds and develops a specific investment policy. Dealer operations with fund securities carried out by the bank on its own account are widespread, their purpose is to profit from the difference in the price of buying and selling securities.

If a commercial bank is carrying out brokerage activities, according to the legislation of Uzbekistan, its operations should be carried out through the stock exchange. Taking this into account, the brokerage function of commercial banks is performed through a network of brokerage offices.

Realizing the advantages of transactions with securities, commercial banks of Uzbekistan were among the first to join the portfolio of forming the national securities market. It is no coincidence that the shares of commercial banks were the first to appear on the stock market of Uzbekistan on the "Tashkent" Republican Stock Exchange in 1994.

The following securities are allowed to be put into circulation by Uzbek banks.

Figure 4. Securities that have the right to act according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Due to their position, capacity and high qualification of employees, commercial banks carry out various transactions with their own securities and securities of other issuers.

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